

D. 7.1 – Programme and summary/outline of the project status and decisions taken at the Kick-off meeting

WP7 – Management and Coordination

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Index

1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. PROJECT MEETING	5
3. PUBLIC EVENT	6
4. WAY FORWARD.....	7
5. ANNEXES	8
ANNEX 1: List of attendees to the project kickoff meeting	8
ANNEX 2: Project Meeting Full Agenda.....	9
ANNEX 3: Public event full agenda.....	10
ANNEX 4: gEneSys KOM power point presentations	11

1. INTRODUCTION

The project gEneSys (Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems) stems from the consideration that the development goals set out by the Agenda 2030 concerning the access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all (SDG7) do not take into appropriate consideration the gender-related biases and barriers that may hinder or impede this access. Taking from this, the project aims to mainstream the SDG5 goals (concerning gender equality) into the SDG7 goals and to contribute to achieve equal participation of women and men in the energy sector. The project activities develop along eight work packages. Beside to the traditional WPs, (e.g., coordination and management (WP7), Ethics (WP8) and Communication and Dissemination (WP6)), the project envisages research activities to better understand the relationships between gender and energy transition/transformation in the extant scientific literature and knowledge communities (WP1) and to interrogate these relationships through ad-hoc designed surveys to knowledgeable actors (“actors of change”) as well as to lay citizens (“recipients of change”) (WP1 and WP2). The project acknowledges the relevance of international cooperation with African partners for the realization of a fair and just energy transition dedicating an entire WP (WP4) to identifying the needs and opportunities in Africa to advance women in energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders. Moreover, the project plans for practical activities to mainstream the project's key themes into the students' and teachers' training and curricula (WP3). Finally, the project seeks to pave the way for a sustainable impact by the development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions (WP5).

Led by the National Research Council of Italy, Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies (CNR-IRPPS), the consortium comprises an impressive line-up of experts and institutions with mixed experiences and backgrounds, spanning from gender experts to researchers on energy-related social issues, to professionals working in R&D of energy systems.

The project started officially on February 1st, 2023. In line with the project timeline, the kickoff meeting was organized at the beginning of M2 (on March 7th and 8th) summoning the representatives from all partner organisations (the list of attendees is available in Annex 1).

The kickoff meeting took place at the CNR Headquarter (Piazzale Aldo Moro, 7 in Rome) and encompassed two full days, divided as follows:

- **Project Meeting** – Tuesday, 7th March (9:30- 17:30) and Wednesday, 8th March (13:00-18:30): presentation of the WPs and common discussion (open to partner organisations only)
- **Public event** – Wednesday, 8th March (10:00 – 13:00): key note speeches and panel discussion (open to public).

2. PROJECT MEETING

The project meeting (see annex 2 for the full agenda) sought to achieve the following objectives.

- Set out common rules of work in the consortium;
- Reach a shared understanding of the project's objectives and workplan;
- Allow the gEneSys policy officer (Ms Jeanne Lenders) and project officer (Ms Katherine Quezada) to explain the EU policy environment where gEneSys operates as well as the European Commission's requests concerning the project management and budget reporting;
- Create a working climate based on collaborative and mutual respect values, whereby the competencies of all the members (including senior and junior staff) are acknowledged and appreciated;
- Understand and possibly resolve bottlenecks that may prevent the smooth collaboration among partner organisations as well as the individual partner organisations' full involvement in the project activities.

In order to reach the above-mentioned objectives, the agenda allowed for enough time for discussion to develop and potential issues to be voiced and discussed. In this view, non-working times (e.g., coffee and lunch breaks, site visits etc.) were considered as an integral part of the project meeting in that they enable the creation of the relationships among project partners that are conducive to the effective implementation of the project's tasks and activities.

Before the project's meeting, the team in charge with WP6 (Communication and Dissemination) shared a project's logo and a power point template (see D6.1. for the communication strategy, forthcoming in M6) to be used in all the presentations concerning gEneSys. Each WP leader was requested to arrange a presentation regarding the activities planned in the WP, how these feeds into/are fed by the activities envisaged in other WPs and a list of open points for discussion. The power point presentations are available in annex 4.

At the end of the meeting, the team agreed on the following decisions/list of actions:

- *Adoption of Microsoft TEAMS as a document repository and collaborative platform.* TEAMS will be employed to guarantee full collaboration among the partners working on the projects' activities. The gEneSys TEAM will be hosted in the CNR TEAMS platform and will be used to share and store working material related to tasks and deliverables, to remotely work jointly on the tasks and deliverables working documents, to get feedback and comments from the partners on such documents and to organize virtual meetings when necessary. The partners stated no obstacles in using TEAMS as a platform for organizing the work of the WPs and for storing relevant resources, as they are collected.
- *Timetable of the steering committee meetings.* In addition to the kickoff meeting (M2), three more steering committee meetings will take place during

the project lifecycle. The consortium agreed that the next meeting will be held in Berlin in M9 and will be organized by Fraunhofer IAO. The following meetings will be possibly organized in presence in Krakow (M19) hosted by Jagiellonian University and London, hosted by Imperial College(M29). Two additional meetings are envisaged to be organized online in M24 and M33 in order to address the issues that could arise in the timeframe between the in-person meetings.

- *Data Management Plan (DMP)*. In line with the project proposal, the first draft of the DMP will be submitted at M6 with all partners' contributions, while the final version will be submitted at M18. The consortium is considering the option to sign joint controllers policies (art.26 GDPR) for the six data collections of the project (T1.5, T2.1, T2.2, T2.3, T4.2, T4.5).
- *Open Science*. The consortium agrees to use the platform Zenodo as the repository for the official documents (e.g., public deliverables or policy briefs). The platform will be embedded within the gEneSys website. For the Open data and codes, the consortium agrees to use the CESSDA platform, with the possibility to use another platform energy-field related not completely identified yet. The consortium agrees to use the Open Research Europe (ORE) system for preprints coming from gEneSys results and data, and pledges to publish exclusively in open access (gold or green).
- *Monitoring and Evaluation*: The gEneSys M&E strategy will encompass two streams, concerning the 1) evaluation of project activities and 2) Evaluation of the stakeholder engagement;
- *Ethics*: in line with the workplan envisaged in the proposal, all the partners agreed to appoint a person from each institution to be part of the Projects' internal ethics committee. All the partners agreed to internally discuss and to appoint a person by the end of April.

3. PUBLIC EVENT

The coordination team took the decision to organize a public launch event of the project with the following objectives:

- Starting the engagement of relevant stakeholders from the very preliminary stages of the project;
- Sharing the gEneSys' vision and objectives with the wider public;
- Involving other CNR's departments and research institutes in the planned project's activities;
- Spurring a public debate on the key themes brought forward by the gEneSys project.

After an initial presentation of the project's vision and main activities, the event featured two key note speeches by:

- Dr Anna Sobczak, DG Energy and European University Institute. Presentation title: *Just Transition and Equality – socio-economic dimensions of a clean energy transition in the framework of EU Green Deal*

- Ms Mara Cossu, Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security. Presentation title: *Sustainability perspectives for Energy transition.*

The speeches were followed by a panel discussion on the role of a gender-sensitive approach in the energy transition moderated by PORTIA with the participation of representatives from all the gEneSys partner organizations in addition to a representative from ENI, an Italian multinational energy company, (external to the consortium). The public event's full agenda is available in annex 3.

4. WAY FORWARD

On the short term, the gEneSys kick off meeting sets the start of a number of activities.

1. *Work Package 1.* The activities of WP1 have now formally started with the collection of relevant resources for the systematic literature review (SLR) and the setting up of the working groups that will work towards the achievement of the SLR's specific objectives.
2. *Engagement with the EUI Florence School of Regulation's Light on Women initiative.* The Coordination team will organize an online meeting with the leaders of the initiatives (Dr Ilaria Conti, Head of Gas at the Florence School of Regulation and Dr Leonardo Meuus, Director of the Florence School of Regulation) in order to discuss future venues of collaboration between the gEneSys project and the EUI initiatives to advance women's participation in the energy transition.

On the side of this, the CNR coordination team announced that it will release two open calls for the recruitment of a research fellow and a senior researcher to work on stakeholder engagement and energy policies analysis respectively.

5. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1: List of attendees to the project kickoff meeting

<i>Partner name</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Surname</i>	<i>Participation mode</i>
FRAUNHOFER INSTITUTE	Sabine	Loos	In-presence
AIMS	Nana Ama Browne	Klutse	In-presence
FRAUNHOFER INSTITUTE	Schraudner	Martina	In-presence
JAGIELLONIAN UNIVERSITY	Marta	Warat	In-presence
PORTIA	Elizabeth	Pollitzer	In-presence
AIMS	Audrey	Namdiero-Walsh	In-presence
JAGIELLONIAN UNIVERSITY	Paulina	Sekuła	In-presence
ENEA	Fabiola L.	Falconieri	In-presence
IMPERIAL COLLEGE	Yara	Evans	In-presence
IMPERIAL COLLEGE	Rocio	Diaz-Chavez	In-presence
ENEA	Antonio	De Nicola	In-presence
ENEA	Tatiana	Patriarca	In-presence
ENEA	VITTORIA maria	PERI	In-presence
ENEA	Gregorio	D'Agostino	In-presence
European Commission	Jeanne	Lenders	In-presence
CNR	Sveva	Avveduto	In-presence
CNR	Lucio	Pisacane	In-presence
CNR	Serena	Tagliacozzo	In-presence
CNR	Fabrizio	Pecoraro	In-presence
CNR	Marco	Cellini	In-presence
CNR	Nicolò	Marchesini	In-presence
VIU	Elisa	Carlotto	Online
VIU	Ilda	Mannino	Online
European Commission	Katherine	Quezada	Online

ANNEX 2: Project Meeting Full Agenda

gEneSys - Kick off Meeting - Agenda

March, 7th and 8th 2023 CNR, Piazzale A Moro, 7 - Rome

March 7th

CNR - Sala multifunzionale (ground floor)

9:00	Registration
9:30	Institutional greetings (Mario Paolucci , CNR-IRPPS Director)
9:40	Presentation of the gEneSys project's objectives, list of partners and relation between WPs (Lucio Pisacane and Serena Tagliacozzo , CNR-IRPPS)
9:50	Roundtable of presentations
10:10	Presentation of the EC policy and project officers (Katherine Quezada , Jeanne Lenders and Pablo Jacome Alvarez)
10:40	Presentation of WP1 - ENEA (40 minutes) + Q&A (20 minutes)
11:40	Coffee break
12:00	Presentation of WP2 – IAO (30 minutes) + Q&A (15 minutes)
12:45	Presentation of WP4 - AIMS (30 minutes) + Q&A (15 minutes)
13:30	Lunch break (Sala 3D)
15:00	Presentation of WP3 - UJ (30 minutes) + Q&A (15 minutes)
15:45	Presentation of WP6 - PORTIA (30 minutes) + Q&A (15 minutes)
16:30	Coffee break
16:45 – 17:30	Discussion
From 20:00	Social Dinner, SAID Restaurant, Via Tiburtina 135

March 8th

CNR – Sala Convegni (ground floor)

10:00	Public event. See separate agenda
13:10	Lunch break (Sala Laguna, ground floor)
14:00	Presentation of WP5 - IC (30 minutes) + Q&A (15 minutes)
14:45	Presentation of WP7 and WP8 – CNR (45 minutes) + Q&A (15 minutes)
15:45	Discussion and conclusions
16:30-18:30	Centrale Montemartini visit (https://www.centralemontemartini.org/en/il_museo/storia_del_museo)

ANNEX 3: Public event full agenda

Funded by
the European Union

gEneSys

Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in
Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems

Public Event

8th March 2023
Sala Convegni – CNR Piazzale Aldo Moro Roma

PROGRAMME

10:00 Institutional greetings: **Mario Paolucci**, CNR - IRPPS Director

10:10 gEneSys vision and activities: **Lucio Pisacane** and **Serena Tagliacozzo**, CNR - IRPPS

10:30 A just transition as a socio-economic dimension of a clean energy transition in the framework of EU Green Deal. Presenter: **Anna Sobczak**, Directorate-General for Energy and European University Institute (EUI)

10:50 Sustainability perspectives for Energy transition. Presenter: **Mara Cossu**, Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security

11:10 Panel discussion. Inclusive energy transition: what role for a gender- sensitive approach?
Moderator: **Elizabeth Pollitzer**, Portia

- **Aleksandra Wagner** - Jagiellonian University: transforming policies
- **Martina Schraudner** - Fraunhofer IAO: transforming society and cultures
- **Rocio Diaz-Chavez** - Imperial College: transforming the environment
- **Eliana De Marchi** - ENI: transforming industrial and economic priorities
- **Antonio De Nicola** - ENEA: transforming technological innovation
- **Nana Ama Browne Klutse** - AIMS: transforming international cooperation

12:30 Q&A

13:00 Concluding remarks: **Maria Chiara Carrozza**, CNR President

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ANNEX 4: gEneSys KOM power point presentations

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society
- under grant agreement no. 101094326

WP1 - Gendered analysis of knowledge creation landscape for energy transition

*Kick-off Meeting
Rome - 7th March, 2023*

*Antonio De Nicola, Tatiana Patriarca, Vittoria Maria Peri, Gregorio D'Agostino (ENEA)
Marco Cellini, Lucio Pisacane, Serena Tagliacozzo (IRPPS-CNR)
Sabine Loos, Clemens Striebing (IAO-Fraunhofer)*

WP1 Tasks

- **T1.1** Systematic literature review to design analytical framework for review of EU and national energy transition-related policy frameworks.
- **T1.2** Defining the mission, agendas, and identifying the change actors in the evolution to sustainable energy systems.
- **T1.3** Gendered assessment of energy-systems-knowledge-community
- **T1.4** Gendered assessment of EU policies for sustainable energy systems
- **T1.5** Gendered assessment of stakeholder organisations in sustainable energy systems

WP1 deliverables

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
D1.1 (T1.1, T1.2)	Systematic literature review of studies at the nexus of gender equality and sustainable energy systems and ontology of energy systems	WP1	1 - CNR-IRPPS	R — Document, report	PU - Public	8 1 st Oct 2023
D1.2 (T1.3, T1.4)	Report on Gendered assessment of the energy systems knowledge community and EU policies for sustainable energy systems(Leader: ENEA, M13)	WP1	3 - ENEA	R — Document, report	PU - Public	13 1 st Mar 2024
D1.3 (T1.5)	A multi-country, comparative, gendered assessment survey of stakeholder organizations in sustainable energy systems.	WP1	1 - CNR-IRPPS	R — Document, report	PU - Public	15 1 st May 2024

T1.1 Systematic Literature Review (SLR) on gender studies and sustainable energy systems

T1.1 Systematic literature review to design analytical framework for review of EU and national energy transition-related policy frameworks. Months: 1-6.

T1.1 will conduct a systematic literature review on gender studies and sustainable energy systems. The review will cover the policy, economic, environmental, cultural, governance, and technological subsystems of the energy transition ecosystem and adopt the Gendered Innovation perspective. This task will facilitate the design of the analytical framework for policy review to be used in T1.4 (Leader: **CNR**, Co-leads: **Imperial, ENEA, UJ, IAO**)

SLR (Tentative) Objectives

SLR-O1. Collecting relevant sources for SLR (i.e. reports from international orgs, scientific journals, ...)

SLR-O2. Defining the energy transition/transformation concept

SLR-O3. Achieving a better understanding of existing approaches for gender studies

SLR-O4. Compiling a systematic overview on the concrete phenomenological manifestations of the Gender/Diversity-Equity-Inclusion(DEI)-Energy nexus

SLR-O5. Extraction of criteria for credible pathways (Obj. to be defined. See WP5)

SLR-O1. Collecting relevant sources

- Identifying international organisations and institutes addressing gender studies. E.g.:
 - Gender and Energy Data Explorer (IEA)
 - G7 Report on Gender Equality & Diversity in the Energy Sector (2022).
 - *ASSET study on collection of gender-disaggregated data on the employment and participation of women and men in the energy sector*, Publications Office, 2021 (EU Com., DG Energy)
- Identifying scientific journals addressing energy-related topics

SLR-02. Defining the energy transition/transformation concept

- *Energy transition refers to the global energy sector's shift from fossil-based systems of energy production and consumption — including oil, natural gas and coal — to renewable energy sources like wind and solar, as well as lithium-ion batteries. [S&P Global]*

Energy transition conceptual framework

- 1 (a)** Energy operations have an impact on environmental conditions.
- 1 (b)** Environmental conditions affect energy operations.
- 2** Energy operations affect energy strategy definition.
- 3 (a)** Energy operations affect energy policy definition.
- 3 (b)** Energy policies affect energy operations.
- 4 (a)** Energy operations affect energy behavior.
- 4 (b)** Energy behavior affects energy operations.
- 5** Energy behavior has an impact on environmental conditions.
- 6 (a)** Energy behavior influences energy strategy definition.
- 6 (b)** Energy strategy affects energy behavior.
- 7 (a)** Energy behavior influences energy policy definition.
- 7 (b)** Energy policies affect energy behavior.
- 8 (a)** The impact of energy policies affects energy strategy definition.
- 8 (b)** Energy strategy drives energy policy definition.
- 9** Environmental conditions affect energy strategy definition.

Row affects column	Environmental layer	Energy strategy layer	Energy policy layer	Energy behavior layer	Energy operation layer
Environmental layer		9	-	5b	1b
Energy strategy layer	-		8b	6b	-
Energy policy layer	-	8a		7b	3b
Energy behavior layer	5	6a	7a		4b
Energy operation layer	1a	2	3a	4a	

SLR-03. Achieving a better understanding of existing approaches for gender studies

- Methods adopted to study gender-based representation in other fields (e.g., computer science)
 - Qualitative approaches
 - Quantitative approaches
 - Agents of change & recipients of change
 - ...
- Gendered Innovations perspective
 - Intersectional approach
-

SLR-O4. Compiling a systematic overview on the concrete phenomenological manifestations of the Gender/Diversity-Equity-Inclusion(DEI)-Energy nexus

Author	Search syntax	Identified articles	Screened articles																														
Jenkins et al. 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Energy justice” Within three fields, the article title, abstract, and keywords. January 2008 and December 2019 	155	155																														
Feenstra & Özerol 2021	<table border="1" data-bbox="402 258 1047 468"> <thead> <tr> <th>Search string</th> <th>Step 1</th> <th>Step 2</th> <th>Step 3</th> <th>Step 4</th> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <th>Searching</th> <th>Scoping</th> <th>Screening</th> <th>Selecting</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>I: gender AND energy</td> <td>11,117</td> <td>332</td> <td>117</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>II: gender AND energy AND policy</td> <td>624</td> <td>318</td> <td>49</td> <td>39</td> </tr> <tr> <td>III: gender AND energy justice</td> <td>54</td> <td>42</td> <td>21</td> <td>16</td> </tr> <tr> <td>IV: energy justice AND energy poverty</td> <td>158</td> <td>96</td> <td>22</td> <td>6</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time frame: 1995 - June 2020 	Search string	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4		Searching	Scoping	Screening	Selecting	I: gender AND energy	11,117	332	117	10	II: gender AND energy AND policy	624	318	49	39	III: gender AND energy justice	54	42	21	16	IV: energy justice AND energy poverty	158	96	22	6	11.953	71
Search string	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4																													
	Searching	Scoping	Screening	Selecting																													
I: gender AND energy	11,117	332	117	10																													
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III: gender AND energy justice	54	42	21	16																													
IV: energy justice AND energy poverty	158	96	22	6																													
Lacey-Barnacle et al. 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We searched WOS for all papers containing the words “Energy” and “Justice” in the title, abstract, author-defined keywords and ‘keywords plus’ (additional set of keywords automatically generated by WOS from the titles articles cited) any publication that looked at developing economies / economies in transition were included 1970 – 7 May 2018 	754	68																														
gEneSys	<p>((ALL=(((gender OR women OR justice) AND "energy transition") OR ((gender OR women OR justice) AND "climate change") OR ((gender OR women OR justice) AND "green new deal") OR ((gender OR women OR justice) AND decarbonization) OR ((gender OR women OR justice) AND "energy transformation") OR ((gender OR women OR justice) AND "green transition")))) AND ALL=(survey OR "quantitative analysis" OR "cross-national"))</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Terms 1: Gender/women/justice Terms 2: Energy transition/climate change/green new deal/decarbonization/energy transformation/green transition Alternative: Only in title, abstract or keywords 	1265 Alternative: 540																															
Further terms	Energy justice, environmental justice, climate justice, indigenous rights, human rights, energy democracy, energy access, energy affordability, just transition, civic agency, energy equity, feminist energy systems, eco-feminism, energy ethics, due process, energy poverty, fuel poverty, gender-energy-nexus																																

Timeline T1.1

SLR-O5. Extraction of criteria for credible pathways

- See WP5

T1.2 Defining the mission, agendas, and identifying the change actors in the evolution to sustainable energy systems.

T1.2 Defining the mission, agendas, and identifying the change actors in the evolution to sustainable energy systems.
Months: 1-7.

T1.2 will build the conceptual framework of conventional and sustainable energy systems by employing widely used ontology engineering methodologies (e.g., UPON and NEON). An ontology is a conceptual model of a fragment of an observed reality gathering interlinked concepts pertaining to a given application domain. It will be built starting from existing ontological models (e.g., the DEHEMS ontology and SAREF4ENER) and will include knowledge related to the social, economic, environmental, and technological spheres underpinning energy transformation and the European Green New Deal. Available data repositories (e.g., SCOPUS abstract and citation database) will also be considered as a source of knowledge. Experts in the field will be involved to contribute and validate the final ontology. (Leader: ENEA, Co-leads: CNR, UJ, IAO, IC, AIMS).

What is an ontology

- An ontology is a formal specification of a shared conceptualization [Gruber93 + Borst97]
- An ontology is a conceptual model of a fragment of an observed reality
- It consists of:
 - A set of concepts
 - A set of relationships between them
 - A set of axioms

Ontology of Energy Systems (OES)

- The *ontology of energy systems* aims at defining the energy system from a multi-dimensional perspective including energy operations, energy behavior, energy policies and strategies, and environment and their inter-relationships.

OES Objectives

- Shared understanding of the energy domain
- Identification of the change actors in the evolution to sustainable energy systems
- Defining the scope of the energy-systems knowledge community
 - Precondition for the task T1.3

Ontology building steps

Six steps, each producing readily usable output

De Nicola, A. and Missikoff, M.: A lightweight methodology for rapid ontology engineering. Communications of the ACM, 59(3):79-86 (2016).

Ontology Design Patterns

- Ontology design patterns are reusable conceptual structures aimed at supporting the ontology engineering process
- From relationships to ontology design patterns
- Conceptual structures

A Gangemi, V Presutti. *Ontology design patterns*. Handbook on Ontologies, 2009.

Ontology Design Patterns: Example

Ontology Validation

Syntactic quality

- Measuring the quality of the ontology according to its formal style, the way it is written

Semantic quality

- Absence of contradictory concepts
- Reasoners (RacerPro, Pellet, FaCT++)

Pragmatic quality

- Referring to the ontology content and usefulness for users
- Fidelity, relevance, completeness
- Competency questions

Social quality

- Degree of social acceptance of the ontology

Ontology Engineering (OE) Approaches

- Top-Down
- Bottom-Up
- Middle-Out

OE: Top-Down example

CONCEPTUALIZATION

Analysis of existing ontologies

sustainability MDPI

Review
Smart City Ontologies and Their Applications: A Systematic Literature Review
 Antonio De Nicola ^{*,†} and Maria Luisa Villani [†]

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^{*} Correspondence: antonio.denicola@enea.it
[†] These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract: The increasing interconnections of city services, the explosion of available urban data, and the need for multidisciplinary analysis and decision making for city sustainability require new technological solutions to cope with such complexity. Ontologies become a viable and effective tool to practitioners for developing applications requiring data and process interoperability, big data management, and automatic reasoning on knowledge. We investigate how and to what extent ontologies have been used to support smart city services and we provide a comprehensive evidence on what problems have been addressed and what has been achieved so far with ontology-based applications. To this purpose, we conducted a systematic literature review focused on presenting the ontologies and the methods and technological systems in which ontologies play a relevant role in shaping smart cities. Based on the result of the review process, we also propose a classification of the sub-domains of the city addressed by the ontologies we found, and the research issues that have been considered so far by the scientific community. We highlight those for which semantic technologies have been mostly demonstrated to be effective to enhance the smart city concept and, finally, discuss in more details about some open problems.

Keywords: smart city; smart energy; smart home; urban planning; crisis management; smart health; smart services; sustainable city; ontologies; semantic technology

Check for updates
 Citation: De Nicola, A., Villani, M.L. Smart City Ontologies and Their Applications: A Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability* **14**, 10000 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s141010000>

OE: Bottom-Up example

- Query SCOPUS to collect journals classified by the topic “energy”
- Query SCOPUS to collect the journals where ENEA researchers published papers
- Select relevant journals
- Query SCOPUS to select all the papers of the selected journals
- Analyze topics
- Build the Energy Ontology

Number of journals classified by the topic "Energy" by Scopus

ENEA scientific production

EO: Middle-Out Approach

Timeline T1.2

T1.3 Gendered assessment of energy-systems-knowledge community

T1.3 Gendered assessment of energy-systems-knowledge-community. Months 8-13

Once the energy system domain is defined, WP1 will retrieve evidence on the corresponding research communities from the SCOPUS database. This community will be analysed as a social network constructed with the help of innovative gendered assessment techniques, using novel indicators, such as network centrality and semantic centrality of researchers. (Leader: ENEA, Co-leads: CNR, UJ, IAO, IC, Portia).

Framework for gender divide assessment in scientific communities

- Exploring the role of the structure of social networks (SN) in the dynamics of SN members interests
- Going beyond representativeness rates
- Analysis at the individual level of specific features characterizing SN members (e.g., authority, susceptibility, network centrality, creativity)

Software architecture

Timeline T1.3

T1.4 Gendered assessment of EU policies for sustainable energy systems.

T1.4. Gendered assessment of EU policies for sustainable energy systems. Months 6-13.

This task will perform a comparative policy analysis of the national recovery and resilience plans elaborated by all EU member states to map and compare how the different countries have incorporated provisions concerning the ‘green deal’, gender equality, and the mission to achieve energy transition. The comparison will pay special attention to how gender equality, diversity, and inclusion have been accounted for and where targeted gender mainstreaming is needed. The analysis will be done through a rigorous and comprehensive text analysis and will cover the economic, environmental, cultural, governance and technological subsystems. The analysis will also explore how policy decisions are made, the expected impact in terms of equity/fairness and the targets of the policies for sustainable energy systems at EU and national level. (Leader: CNR, Co-leads: ENEA, UJ, IAO, IC, Portia).

T1.4. Gendered assessment of EU policies for sustainable energy systems

Objectives:

- Build the evidence base on structural and cultural forms of discrimination that act as barriers to women's full participation in energy systems and energy transition.

Activities:

- Comparative policy analysis of the national recovery and resilience plans to map how EU countries have incorporated provisions concerning the 'green deal', gender equality, and the mission to achieve energy transition.
- The analysis will be done through a rigorous and comprehensive text analysis and will cover the economic, environmental, cultural, governance and technological subsystems.
- The analysis will also explore how policy decisions are made, the expected impact in terms of equity/fairness and the targets of the policies for sustainable energy systems at EU and national level.
- Months 6-13.

Timeline T1.4

T1.5 Gendered assessment of stakeholder organisations in sustainable energy systems

T1.5. Gendered assessment of stakeholder organisations in sustainable energy systems. Months: 6-15

This task we will define an analytic hierarchy process (AHP) survey, containing detailed questions about women's participation and empowerment in energy transition, specifically collecting workers' opinions on the future of energy sector in terms of: i) professional needs of workers; ii), the relationship between women and the energy sector with regard to gender stereotypes and the skills of women workers; iii) strategies to attract young people to the study of STEM subjects, taking into account obstacles as well as potentials; iv) availability of existing statistics, source, robustness of gender data. The questions will be tested with at least 10 pilot qualitative interviews with researchers and key informants in the involved RPO. The survey will involve stakeholder organisations operating in the sector of energy transition in four European countries participating in the project (i.e., Germany, Italy, Poland, UK) to identify differences and similarities concerning women within the energy sector. (Leader: **CNR**, Co-leads: **ENEA, UJ, IAO, IC, Portia**).

T1.5. Gendered assessment of stakeholder organizations in sustainable energy systems M: 6-15

Objectives:

- Build the evidence base on structural and cultural forms of discrimination that act as barriers to women's full participation in energy systems and energy transition.

Activities:

- Design a survey containing questions about women's participation and empowerment in energy transition, collecting workers' opinions terms of:
 - professional needs of workers
 - the relationship between women and the energy sector regarding gender stereotypes and the skills of women workers
 - strategies to attract young people to the study of STEM subjects
- The survey design will be informed by the results from tasks 1.1, 1.3, 1.4, and tested with 10 pilot qualitative interviews within involved RPO.
- The survey will involve stakeholder organizations operating in the sector of energy transition in four European countries (i.e., Germany, Italy, Poland, UK) to identify differences and similarities concerning women within the energy sector.

T1.5 Stakeholders to be involved

- Submit the survey to representative organisations in 4 EU countries
 - Italy: CNR, ENEA, ENI?, ...
 - Germany: ...
 - Poland: ...
 - UK:

Timeline: T1.5

Relationships with the other workpackages

WP7 Management + WP8 Ethics

Discuss WP1 & WP2 relationship

	01/02/23	01/03/23	01/04/23	01/05/23	01/06/23	01/07/23	01/08/23	01/09/23	01/10/23	01/11/23	01/12/23	01/01/24	01/02/24	01/03/24	01/04/24
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15
WP1 - Gendered analysis of knowledge creation landscape for energy transition															
T1.1 Systematic literature review to design analytical framework for review of EU and national energy transition-related policy frameworks.								D1.1							
T1.2 Defining the mission, agendas, and identifying the change actors in the evolution to sustainable energy systems.								D1.1							
T1.3 Gendered assessment of energy-systems-knowledge-community.														D1.2	
T1.4. Gendered assessment of EU policies for sustainable energy systems.													D1.2		
T1.5. Gendered assessment of stakeholder organisations in sustainable energy systems.															D1.3

Thank You !

Work Package 2

Exploring gendered intersectional patterns in citizen's behaviours and orientations towards energy transition

Prof. Dr. Martina Schraudner, Dr. Clemens Striebing, Sabine Loos (Fraunhofer CeRRI)

Work Package 2: Overarching goal

WP2 is the vehicle for collecting and analyzing novel data on **citizens' behaviours and attitudes** towards the **energy transition** with an **intersectional approach** integrated from the beginning.

Task 2.1: Exploring intersectional power-gender relations

Goal

Identification of patterns of **intersectionality** in **participation, values, and behavior of citizens**.
Explanation of differences in citizens' support and engagement in the energy transition.

Method

Questionnaire survey

- across several countries in Europe and Africa
- with a total case number of 30,000 respondents,
- equally distributed across 10 countries, including 6 EU member states and 4 Sub-Saharan African countries

Deliverables

Report with analytical model

Task 2.2: Co-creation with a group of experts in the field of energy transition and intersectionality

Goal

Gaining a deeper understanding of the data patterns explored in T2.1 and validate the results with experts at the intersection of energy & gender/justice/intersectionality

Method

- Identification of an expert panel (10-15 experts from them gEneSys Advisory Board and beyond)
- Delphi survey with the expert panel using the exploratory report from T2.1
 - Questions to assess the theoretical understanding of the explored data patterns
 - Summary of the assessments mirrored to all group members
 - Potential modifications

Deliverables

- Report on survey results
- Theoretical framework report

Task 2.3: Case study analysis

Goal

Validate the applicability of the theoretical framework developed in T2.2. in specific energy transition cases and further improve the theoretical framework

Method

- Test the applicability of the theoretical framework in concrete cases of the energy transition
 - Case identification (10 African and European countries)
 - Collection of micro, meso, and macro data
 - Development of an interview guide
 - 60 interviews with individuals (45 min) conducted by the service provider

Deliverables

- Case study report

Task 2.4: Providing concrete implications for policy actions

Goals

Derivation of policy implications tackling intersectional energy injustices in the energy transition

Method

- Summarizing lessons learned
- Derivation of implications for political and civil society actors (for WP3)

Deliverables

- Final report

Our current challenge: What does intersectionality in the context of the energy transition mean and how can it be operationalized?

Our current challenge: **What does intersectionality in the context of the energy transition mean** and how can it be operationalized?

“An **intersectional** approach to gender is to analyse social inequalities and **systems of power** with the awareness of their **interconnected** character, such as how **gender** inequality interacts with other inequalities of **ethnicity, race, class** and **age**.”

Johnson et al. 2020

Our current challenge: What does intersectionality in the context of the energy transition mean and **how can it be operationalized?**

Our goal is to explore **marginalization processes** and thereby investigate how **marginalized identities are (re)produced** in the context of the energy transition.

To this end, we want to combine a **sociological, political and socio-psychological approach** in our theoretical model.

Model measuring intersectional injustices in the energy transition

Context factors

- Household's current energy mix
- Energy access & availability
- Acceptance of RET & policies
- Regional/cultural/political context
- Perception of debate about energy transition
- Energy plant/infrastructure in neighborhood
- Electricity source's mix
- ...

Identity (sociodemographic indicators)

- Gender
- Age
- Income
- Education
- Job
- Ethnicity/Race
- Urban/rural/inner-country peripheries and islands
- Country
- Religion
- Indigenous group

Marginalization Processes

- Direct oppression by another social group
- Bias & prejudice towards minorities (social identity theory), measured by self-perception as belonging to a minority, micro aggressions
- Societal expectations (social role theory), measured by masculinity-femininity scale, scales for household responsibilities
- ...

Experiences of Marginalization

- Distributive Justice:** Distribution of benefits and burdens of energy infrastructure & systems [concern]
- Money
 - Work
 - Education
 - Time
 - Health
 - Environment
 - Safety
 - Quality of life / Wellbeing
- Procedural Justice:** incorporation of marginalized perspectives in decision-making [strategies]
- Knowledge/Information access
 - Power / Decision making / Participation
 - Legal rights

Marginalized Identity Self-Perception

- Justice in recognition:** consideration given to knowledge, values, norms of those affected [who]
- Internal Political Efficacy (believe in own competence)
 - External Political Efficacy (believe in the chance to be heard by politics)
 - Legitimacy belief in energy policy
 - Legitimacy belief in energy transition policy

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WP3

Development of Concrete Solutions to Advance Women in Energy Transition

Paulina Sekuła, Aleksandra Wagner, Marta Warat, Jagiellonian University, Sabine Loos, Clemens Striebing, Fraunhofer

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WP3: General description

- **Duration:** 6M – 32M
- **Effort:** 52 PMs
- **Leading:** UJ, **CO-leading:** All partners
- **Aims:**
 - developing solutions to improve girls' and women's understanding of energy transition jobs and careers panorama as well as their career aspirations and professional involvement in transforming energy landscape from unsustainable to sustainable,
 - promoting gender sensitive education for energy transition.
- **Methodology:** Theory of change.

What is Theory of Change

- The development of the solutions is driven by the logic of Theory of Change which is a **structured technique for understanding how a programme or set of solutions is likely to contribute to a long- term change.**

The method is transdisciplinary and focuses on the actors (individuals and groups) active in the context of change, identifying what needs to be changed and why. It is a reflexive, evidence- based system learning oriented to achieve impact (improvements in policy and practice).

Theory of change as an approach: combining research with development goals

- Theory of change can help to strengthen the planning, implementation and evaluation of impact strategies **for an impact-oriented research project.**
- theory of change helps research teams to map out the anticipated links between their research project, the issues and context they are seeking to influence, and the longer-term social, development and environmental outcomes
- It has roots in evaluation and action research

Theory of change: 'Description of a sequence of events expected to lead to a particular desired outcome', Rick Davies

CONTEXTUAL DRIVERS

Socio-economic, political, Technological factors

Existing policies, practices, beliefs

Actors, stakeholders, networks in research, policy and practice, power relations

Capacity of target groups to respond to and use research

Receptiveness of context

Organizations, resources, systems, skills

LONG-TERM, LASTING CHANGES

MEDIUM TERM CHANGES

Sphere of indirect influence – *policy shapers, knowledge networks, planners, practitioners, stakeholder groups*

SHORT-TERM CHANGES

Sphere of direct influence – *partners, collaborators, stakeholders immediate programme target groups*

Sphere of control
Programme strategy: Activities, stakeholder engagement; outputs

Outputs = products + comms + networks

Awareness + engagement of stakeholders

Use by main actor / stakeholder groups

Changes in e.g. knowledge, attitudes, skills, relationships

Changes in e.g. practices, policies, allocations

Scaling up/out of changes in knowledge, practices, policies through actor networks etc.

Impact

For whom?
Defined by whom?
Significant for whom?
Research's contribution?

What needs to be happening to support this change?

Adapted from Montague, 2011

Theory of change as a process

- theory of change is a dialogue-based process intended to generate a *'description of a sequence of events that is expected to lead to a particular desired outcome.'*(Vogel 2022)

How to develop the theory of change?

- **Stage 1: Context for the initiative:** analysis of the current state of the problem the project is seeking to influence, the social, political and environmental conditions, and other actors able to influence change.
- **Stage 2: Long-term change:** a statement expressing the long-term change that the initiative seeks to support, from whose perspective it is significant and for whose ultimate benefit.
- **Stage 3: Sequence of events:** mapping the sequence of changes that lead to the desired long-term outcome.
- **Stage 4: Assumptions:** critical reflection on the change process, making explicit the analytical perspectives on change, the drivers of change and expressing the underlying hypotheses about how these changes could come about. The purpose of making these assumptions explicit is as a check on whether the activities and outputs are appropriate for influencing change in the desired direction in this context.
- **Stage 5: Diagram and narrative summary:** creating a diagram and narrative that represents the sequence and captures the discussion.

WP3 Tasks

- T3.1 Improve awareness of and education on sustainability and energy transition among pre-school and school age students (Months: 6-18)
- T3.2 Analyse and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the fossil fuel-based vs. the renewable energy systems (Months: 8-24)
- T3.3 Increase the participation of women in energy systems and in advancing energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders (Months: 24-32)
- T3.4 Promote gender sensitive approaches to energy transition in research, innovation and Higher Education (Months: 25-32)

T3.1 Improve awareness of and education on sustainability and energy transition among pre-school and school age students (Months: 6-18; Leader: UJ, Colead: ENEA, Imperial, IAO)

Goal

- Supporting primary and secondary school teachers and education policy makers in identifying gender bias in textbooks and introducing the gender perspective in education on energy transition
- Raising awareness to prevent teachers from unconsciously introducing gender bias

Method

- Mapping and analysis of teaching materials and curricula, identification of methods and tools for gender sensitive education
- Input from related efforts in Physics and Engineering

Result

- Guidelines for teachers and for education policy makers for introducing the gender perspective in teaching energy transition

T3.2 Analyse and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the fossil fuel-based vs. the renewable energy systems (Months: 8-24; Leader: UJ, Co-lead: Portia, Imperial, IAO, AIMS)

Goal

- Understanding female tertiary students' attitudes to careers in energy sectors
- Supporting HEIs in developing gender sensitive pedagogies and career advice

Method

- participatory and co-creation approaches involving university students and teachers

Result

- Policy briefs on intersectional and gender-sensitive energy transformation: analyses and recommendations to help universities revise their pedagogies and career advice by paying attention to the values of inclusion, sustainability, justice, and fairness when promoting skills and careers for the 'green new deal' panorama or jobs and careers

T3.3 Increase participation of women in energy systems and in advancing energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders (Months: 24-32; Leader: UJ, Co-lead: Imperial, IAO)

Goal

- advancing women into energy transition processes as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and change leaders

Method

- Results from WP1, WP2, WP3.2, WP3.3 and WP5
- Collection and analysis of existing programmes and best practice in Europe and beyond
- participatory, reflexive national workshops with female researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders to design long-term impact on energy landscape

Result

- International masterclass on pedagogy and training on gender aspects of energy transition
- Information pack for use by African Institute of Mathematical Sciences to engage more women in their researcher training programmes

T3.4 Promote gender sensitive approaches to energy transition in research, innovation and Higher Education (Months: 25-32)

Goal

- Supporting higher education and research institutes in incorporating gender perspectives in education programmes

Method

- Build on the results from WP5 on integrating gender perspectives into the EUA's recommendations for how universities can facilitate energy transition through research, innovation, and education
- Develop and advance approaches for higher education and research institutes to incorporate gender perspectives in their training programmes

Result

- Toolbox with good practices and new methods for teaching materials and curriculum

WP3 Deliverables & Milestones

Deliverables

- D3.1 – Guidance notes for education policy makers on integrating gender perspective into all levels of education on transitions in energy system (18M, UJ)
- D3.2 – Policy briefs on intersectional and gender-sensitive energy transformation (30M, UJ)
- D3.3 – Analyses of and recommendations for training programmes on gender sensitive energy transition (28M, UJ)
- D3.4 – Toolbox with good practices and new methods in teaching materials and curriculum (32M, Fraunhofer)

Milestones

- Reflexive national workshops (30M, UJ)
- International masterclass on pedagogy and training on gender aspects of energy transition (32M, UJ)

Partners' involvement in WP3

Participant	T3.1	T3.2	T3.3	T3.4
1. CNR				Co-lead
2. UJ	Leader	Leader	Leader	Co-lead
3. ENEA	Co-lead			
4. Fraunhofer	Co-lead	Co-lead	Co-lead	Leader
5. AIMS Rwanda		Co-lead		Co-lead
6. Portia gGmbH		Co-lead		Co-lead
7. Imperial	Co-lead	Co-lead	Co-lead	Co-lead

Partners' involvement in WP3

Participant	PMs in WP3
1. CNR	6.00
1.1. VIU	
2. UJ	24.00
3. ENEA	8.00
4. Fraunhofer	3.00
5. AIMS Rwanda	5.00
6. Portia gGmbH	3.00
7. Imperial	3.00
Total Person-Months	52.00

WP3 and other WPs

- WP2 utilises the results of WP1, WP2 and WP5, and contributes to WP4 on matters of international cooperation and contextual drivers of change. The whole process combines the availability of quality evidence and stakeholders' engagement to **achieve the aware reception of new knowledge and improve capacity to respond to it.**
- To maximise the opportunity of impact, WP3 will establish vital contacts with leaders of change and thanks to their contextualised experience will collectively assess the new knowledge (WP1 and WP2 result) and develop new applications for policy and practice in advancing women as change agents and change recipients in energy transition ecosystem on equal terms to men.

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Work Package 4

Transforming International cooperation between Europe and Africa on advancing gender participation

Prof Nana Ama Browne KLUTSE, PI, AIMS-Canada Researcher, African Institute of Mathematical Sciences (AIMS)

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AIMS

African Institute for
Mathematical Sciences
NEXT EINSTEIN INITIATIVE

WE ARE LEADING AFRICA'S SOCIO-ECONOMIC TRANSFORMATION THROUGH:

Innovative
scientific training

Technical advances
& discoveries

Strategic foresight
and policy design

HOW ARE WE DOING THIS?

A I M S E C O S Y S T E M O F T R A N S F O R M A T I O N

Introduction to WP4

- WP4 will exploit opportunities for international cooperation between Europe and Africa, in and through
 - Horizon Europe,
 - UN Sustainable Development Agenda,
 - UN Women,
 - UNESCO educational initiatives,
 - Gender Summit-Africa,
 - National research funding mechanisms in Europe for women researchers in Africa,
 - and the support mechanisms in Europe that target women innovators and entrepreneurs, etc.
- Specific attention will be given to the European Parliament's call for cooperation between EU and Africa on
 - SDGs,
 - entrepreneurship, and
 - leadership training programmes.

We are guided by the SDGs

The work package will

Review the past and active research and innovation cooperation programmes

Identify the needs and opportunities to advance women in Africa as energy transition researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders

Identify opportunities, instruments, and mechanisms to operationalise the European Parliament's recommendations for cooperation on SDGs implementation

Analyse how the concepts of equity, inclusion, justice, and fairness in the context of SDG7 targets are interpreted by various stakeholders in Africa

Expected Deliverables

- Report on past and current international cooperation initiatives between Europe and Africa
- Mechanisms and instruments for operationalising EU-Africa cooperation on implementing SDGs
- Conceptualising and operationalising the values of equity, justice, fairness, and sustainability in African research and innovation

Partners on WP4

Work package number	4	Lead beneficiary					AIMS
Work package title	International cooperation between Europe and Africa						
Participant number	1	5	8	4	6	3	7
Short name of participant	CNR	ENEA	PORTIA	J.U.	IAO	I.C.	AIMS
Person months per participant:	4	3	4	3	3	3	18
Start month	12			End month	35		

Current status

- WP4 will use the 4th Gender Summit Africa (GS23), planned for June 2023, to collect data on understandings and approaches to just energy transitions.
- Summit's Theme: *Africa's energy transition pathways and vision of the Green New Deal through a gender lens.*
- Summit pre-events, aka GS23 Hubs, hosted in 5 countries (1-2 June 2023): Rwanda, South Africa, Cameroon, Ivory Coast, & Kenya.
- GS23 Hubs will involve various stakeholders & explore how goals and processes for a just energy transition are perceived in those local contexts.
- **Expected outcome of GS23 Hub discussions:** The conceptualization of energy sufficiency in Africa from a gender equality perspective.

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WP5 Development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions

Dr Rocio Diaz-Chavez, Senior Research Fellow, Centre for Environmental Policy
Dr Yara Evans, Research Associate, Centre for Environmental Policy

WP7 Management + WP8 Ethics

WP6 dissemination

Partners

- Imperial College (WP Leader)
- UJ UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLONSKI
- Portia
- CNR CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE
- ENEA AGENZIA NAZIONALE PER LE NUOVE TECNOLOGIE, L'ENERGIA E LO SVILUPPO ECONOMICO SOSTENIBILE
- Fraunhofer
- AIMS AFRICAN INSTITUTE FOR MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES-NEXT EINSTEIN INITIATIVE

WP5 addresses specific challenge (I)

- Dismantle structural and systematic roots of unequal power distribution between women and men on all levels
- promotes women's social and economic empowerment.
- Differing cultural contexts across the EU and among Associated and third countries

WP5: addressing the challenge (II)

- Identify and reverse gender biases and gaps in the knowledge underpinning the discourse on equitable, just, and fair energy transition.
- Any gender biases in the energy transition processes and outcomes are likely to propagate existing structural and systematic roots of unequal power distribution between women and men that prevent women from having equal chances to men to participate in, influence, and benefit from socio-technical transformations.
- WP5 draws on the results from WP1 and WP2 and is guided by the Advisory Board to establish criteria of what is a “credible pathway”.
- WP5 corrects gender biases in the recommendation for research, innovation and education made in the EUA report and in the 400 SSH priority questions proposed by Energy SHIFTS.

Energy-SHIFTS “Energy Social sciences & Humanities Innovation Forum Targeting the SET-Plan”

- Contributes to a European Energy Union Strategic Energy Technology Plan or ‘SET-Plan’, that places societal needs centrally, by further developing Europe’s leadership in using and applying energy-related Social Sciences and Humanities (energy-SSH) (EU Horizon project)
- EU Energy-SHIFTS project identified 400 social science and humanities priority research questions in four energy areas (100 questions each): renewables, smart consumption, energy efficiency and transport and mobility
- The project identified 20 keywords to guide multidisciplinary research, but none refers to “gender”. A total of 20 out of the 400 questions refer to “gender” but in the ‘renewables’ category, it is only one among the 100 questions: “What are the key gaps in understanding the relation of gender equality with energy transitions (i.e., the shift to renewable energy)?”

SSH 400 questions

SDG7 Targets

7.1 By 2030, ensure universal access to affordable, reliable and modern energy services

7.2 By 2030, increase substantially the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix

7.3 By 2030, double the global rate of improvement in energy efficiency

7.A By 2030, enhance international cooperation to facilitate access to clean energy research and technology, including renewable energy, energy efficiency and advanced and cleaner fossil-fuel technology, and promote investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology

7.B By 2030, expand infrastructure and upgrade technology for supplying modern and sustainable energy services for all in developing countries, in particular least developed countries, small island developing States, and land-locked developing countries, in accordance with their respective programmes of support

Key deployment milestones for bioenergy

	2020	2030	2050
Total energy supply (EJ)	63	72	102
Share of advanced biomass feedstock	27%	85%	97%
Modern gaseous bioenergy (EJ)	2.1	5.4	13.7
Biomethane	0.3	2.3	8.3
Modern liquid bioenergy (mboe/d)	1.6	6.0	7.0
Advanced biofuels	0.1	2.7	6.2
Modern solid bioenergy (EJ)	32	54	74
Traditional use of solid biomass (EJ)	25	0	0
Million people using traditional biomass for cooking	2 340	0	0

Notes: mboe/d = million barrels of oil equivalent per day. Bioenergy from forest plantings is considered advanced when forests are sustainably managed (see section 2.7.2).

Uncertainties in NZE and bioenergy

Reduction in total final consumption due to behavioral changes by fuel in the NZE

- Specially the roles played by bioenergy, carbon capture and behavioural changes
- NZE is a path (not only possibility)
- Technology development
- Global cooperation
- Transitions: ensuring the security of fuel
- and electricity supplies at

IEA. All rights reserved.

The impact of behaviour changes and materials efficiency on final energy consumption increases over time

Description**DESCRIPTION OF WORK****T5.1 TASK 5.1 Identification of criteria for the selection of a model pathway** Task Leader: IC; Contributors: UJ, PORTIA (M6-M18)

This task will include two subtasks to identify and apply the criteria in a “model” pathway for the later co-creation of subsequent pathways that will mainstream gender into socio-technical systems. i) review of the literature and data collected in WP1-3 to select criteria for the pathways; ii) propose 1 “model” pathway using the criteria for the co-creation of alternative pathways with social actors to propose credible scenarios for the implementation of the pathways. The non-exhaustive list of potential candidate theories includes: Sociotechnical Transitions, Social Practice Theory, Discourse Theory, Domestication Theory, Large Technical Systems, Social Construction of Technology, Sociotechnical Imaginaries, Actor-Network Theory, Social Justice Theory, Sociology of Expectations, Sustainable Development, Values Beliefs Norms Theory, Lifestyle Theory, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology, and Social Life Cycle Assessment (Lead: IC, Co-lead: CNR, IAO, UJ)

T5.2 Integrating gender perspectives into Energy SHIFTS Months 1-12

T5.2 will analyse each of the questions recommended by Energy SHIFTS to identify if it is necessary to add a gender perspective to the topic with a key source of evidence included to validate the decision. To conduct this assessment, T5.2 will apply the Gendered Innovation approach. The results will contribute to development of “credible” pathways by improving opportunities for social innovation in energy transition processes. (Leader: IC, Co-leads: CNR,UJ, IAO, Imperial, ENEA, Portia)

T5.3 Integrating gender perspectives into EUA recommendations for research, innovation, and education to achieve the mission of energy transition. Months 15-30

T5.3 will analyse the EUA recommendations at three levels: research, innovation, and education to identify gender gaps and propose additional explanation of relevant gender perspectives. The results will help advance the use of Responsible Research and Innovation in achieving equitable, just, and fair energy transitions. (Leader: IC, Co-leads: IAO, ENEA, UJ, CNR, Portia)

WP 5

Imperial College
London

TASK 5.4 Co-creation of pathways and analysis of scenarios with a backcasting methodology Task Leader: IC; Contributors: Portia, CNR, ENEA) (M15-M33)

This task will entail working closely with key stakeholders for the co-creation of credible and sustainable pathways that transform gender power relations and enable a fair and just energy transition. The backcasting analysis allows for understanding how stakeholders envisage future scenarios by working backwards from the desired future scenarios proposed through to the current situation. This methodology is used for planning and therefore it is highly suitable for the analysis of scenarios for the energy sector and gender mainstreaming as it may help to implement the pathways for low-carbon energy efficiency while improving social and climate justice, equity, security, and safety.

This task entails co-creating scenarios and using 'backcasting' methodology for assessing the co-created pathways for their implementation. Backcasting' will be used with stakeholders at workshops to be co-organised with partners in WP6.

T5.5 Review research questions and innovation opportunities for SDG7 Targets. Months 30-36

T5.5 will correct to the gender-blind appearance of SDG7 targets, the text of which makes no reference to gender, women, boys, girls etc. by connecting the targets to the gender perspectives identified in other tasks. The results will promote gender sensitive research and innovation for SDGs and integration of gender perspectives in SDG implementation efforts. (Leader: Portia, Co-lead: IC, AIMS)

WP 5 Deliverables

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
D5.1	Report on selected indicators for pathways model	WP5	7 - Imperial	R — Document, report	PU - Public	18
D5.2	D5.2 Report on gender perspective into energy SHIFTS	WP5	7 - Imperial	R — Document, report	PU - Public	12
D5.3	D5.3 Integrating gender perspectives into EUA recommendations for research, innovation, and education	WP5	7 - Imperial	R — Document, report	PU - Public	30
D5.4	D5.4 Analysis of co-created pathways and scenarios	WP5	7 - Imperial	R — Document, report	PU - Public	33

Cont.

Deliverable D5.1 – Report on selected indicators for pathways model

Deliverable Number	D5.1	Lead Beneficiary	7. Imperial
Deliverable Name	Report on selected indicators for pathways model		
Type	R — Document report	Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Due Date (month)	18	Work Package No	WP5

Description			
Report on selected indicators for pathways model (Leader, IC, M12)			

Deliverable D5.2 – D5.2 Report on gender perspective into energy SHIFTS

Deliverable Number	D5.2	Lead Beneficiary	7. Imperial
Deliverable Name	D5.2 Report on gender perspective into energy SHIFTS		
Type	R — Document report	Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Due Date (month)	12	Work Package No	WP5

Description			
D5.2 Report on gender perspective into energy SHIFTS			

Deliverable D5.3 – D5.3 Integrating gender perspectives into EUA recommendations for research, innovation, and education

Deliverable Number	D5.3	Lead Beneficiary	7. Imperial
Deliverable Name	D5.3 Integrating gender perspectives into EUA recommendations for research, innovation, and education		
Type	R — Document report	Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Due Date (month)	30	Work Package No	WP5

Description			
D5.3 Integrating gender perspectives into EUA recommendations for research, innovation, and education			

Deliverable D5.4 – D5.4 Analysis of co-created pathways and scenarios

Deliverable Number	D5.4	Lead Beneficiary	7. Imperial
Deliverable Name	D5.4 Analysis of co-created pathways and scenarios		
Type	R — Document report	Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Due Date (month)	33	Work Package No	WP5

Description			
D5.4 Analysis of co-created pathways and scenarios			

Core Analytical Methods (I)

- Participatory and co-creation methods for engaging significant change
- Engaging stakeholders academic, policy experts, and practitioners in joint consultations and consensus on credible
- pathways to 'green' and equitable energy systems with concrete implications for policy and actions,
- innovative gender mainstreaming measures, training & career support (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6)

Core Analytical Methods (II)

- Systems/model/scenario thinking to identify intersectional power-gender relations and
- pathways to 'inclusive', 'just', and equitable' energy transition identifying who are the change
- agents and key stakeholders, what are their agendas, what change-oriented mechanisms and
- instruments are already available, what evidence can help facilitate consensus on where
- improvements are needed, and what actions can be taken in the short-, medium-, and long-term
- (WP1, WP2, WP5).

Core Analytical Methods (III)

- Systematic review of academic and policy literature to develop analytical framework for
- policy analysis and to guide gendered assessment of energy communities of knowledge, change
- actors, stakeholder organisations, and EU policies (WP1, WP5)

Core Analytical Methods (IV)

- Creating credible pathways for just and equitable energy transition (WP5)
- Engage in co-creation of credible and sustainable pathways to equitable, just and inclusive energy transition
- Outcomes that are needed and measurable and with processes that are implementable because of available and persuasive evidence on inequalities
- consensus among change actors, stakeholders and change recipient on where transformations in power-gender relations can be achieved
- promoting implementations of gender mainstreaming and gender budgeting measures where they are missing, and through
- integration of gender knowledge into policies, mechanisms and instruments used to achieve energy transition and into social and technical innovation for socio-economic development, including the SDGs.

Co-creation pathways and backcasting (Task 5.4)

- With key stakeholders for the co-creation of credible and sustainable pathways that transform gender power relations and enable a fair and just energy transition.
- The backcasting analysis allows for understanding how stakeholders envisage future scenarios by working backwards from the desired future scenarios proposed through to the current situation .
- This methodology is used for planning and therefore it is highly suitable for the analysis of scenarios for the energy sector and gender mainstreaming as it may help to implement the pathways for low-carbon energy efficiency while improving social and climate justice, equity, security, and safety.
- Backcasting' will be used with stakeholders at workshops to be co-organised with partners in WP6.

HSDB

France

Main indicators assessment, hotspot database HSDB

Diaz-Chavez, 2013)

(Diaz-Chavez, 2015)

Sustainable issues to consider (not exhaustive)

Environment

- Promote healthy lands and forests
- Adhere to internationally accepted carbon accounting rules including certification
- Support forest to store C and protect habitats (NBS)
- Robust science and LCA
- Alternative feedstocks, agricultural residues, waste

Social

- Protect/Invest communities and respect indigenous groups
- Consider all stakeholders and public opinion
- Job creation along the whole supply chain
- Consider **Just transitions**

Techno-economic and logistics

- Invest in technologies to reduce the use of fuel wood for cooking in Global South and promote modern bioenergy
- Consider efficiency in heating and other industrial uses
- Promote BECCS OR CCSU with biomass
- Transform existing infrastructure (pipelines) to be used for H, BioLPG, and other biofuels

Social Actors and Acceptance

Knowledge about the (bioeconomy) is growing as it expands but

- wider society still largely ignorant of what it is/means/does
- different social actors understand it in different ways

Yet, mainstreaming of the bioeconomy depends on social acceptance and take-up of bioproducts:

‘The best technology does no good unless people use it’ (Wegener and Kelly, 2008:107)

Need to examine the factors condition the social acceptance of bioeconomy value chains

- How different social groups understand the bioeconomy?

Social Perception and Acceptance

Social acceptance:

- the societal embedding and adoption of technologies and applications, their products and services
- increasingly acknowledged as essential for their successful development and market diffusion
- impacts on the development of (bioeconomy) projects, infrastructure, chains, and policies
- of biofuels (a sector in the bioeconomy) is particularly well documented
- takes varied forms; involves a range of 'social actors' (various stakeholders and the wider public)

Social acceptance is influenced by several factors:

- awareness, knowledge, opinions, attitudes, and behaviour
- perceptions of risks and benefits of technologies and their products
- perceptions of their wider societal, economic, environmental and policy dimensions

Tradeoffs and synergies and social issues.

(Diaz-Chavez et al, 2014)

All Donors to Developing countries unspecified for All sectors & objectives during 2002–2018

Development finance commitments to Developing countries unspecified came from different funders, as shown in the figure. The largest amounts were \$453 billion to Developing countries unspecified.

All Donors to Africa (all) for All sectors & objectives during 2002–2018

Strategic view

Thank You !

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Work Package 6

Dissemination and Impact

Elizabeth Pollitzer, Director, Portia gGmbH

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Objectives

- Support the overall objectives and activities of the project (visual identity, website, attendance at external events etc.)
- Engage multiple target audiences in the transition landscape (conference, workshops, dialogues etc.)
- Engage with other projects for collaboration on gender analysis
- Promote gender dimension into Agenda 2030 activities
- Summer school at Venice International U. (VIU)

A role for every partner

Work package number	6	Lead beneficiary						PORTIA
Work package title	Dissemination and Impact							
Participant number	1	5	8	4	6	3	7	2
Short name of participant	CNR	ENEA	PORTIA	J.U.	IAO	I.C.	AIMS	VIU
Person months per participant:	8	10	21	3	3	2	6	1
Start month	1			End month	36			

Deliverables

D6.1 & D6.2 Communication, Dissemination and Impact strategy

D6.3 Report on who are the actors and stakeholders in energy transition for SDGs

D6.4 Sustainability strategy and action report

D6.5 gEneSys engagement and impact report

Click to add text

Current status

- ✓ Visual and social media identity created
- ✓ Website – core pages designed and implemented
- ✓ Database of relevant projects (~35 EU funded) started
- ✓ gEneSys parallel session at GS22-Europe
- ✓ Link to EU CINEA funded project developing gender indicators for R&I in energy transition
- ✓ Portia and AIMS designed multi-stakeholder participatory session for GS-Africa to be held on 1-2 June 2023 (for T4.2)
- ✓ Portia and AIMS are developing workshop design for gender analysis in implementation of SDG7 (for Task 4.5)

Web/social media identity

- Twitter [@gEneSys_horizon](https://twitter.com/gEneSys_horizon)
- LinkedIn Group: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12786780/>
- [#genesys_eu](https://twitter.com/genesys_eu)
- www.genesys-project.eu

What (immediately) next

- Create Cloud space for sharing & recording partners' communication and dissemination activities
- Draft, consult and prepare D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Impact strategy (Leader: Portia, M6)
- Create and make accessible on the website relevant content: produced by the project and collected from external sources (links to evidence, research, policy briefs, projects, websites, etc.). Get feedback from the Advisory Board

Summer School at Venice International University

M26-36, Leader: VIU and CNR

A one-week summer school will be hosted by VIU, on the island of San Servolo campus, in Venice:

- **target: 20 students** from different countries
- students will be selected through an **open call** that will be disseminated through the **gEneSys partners' networks** and the **VIU network**, that includes universities and research institutions from North America, Europe, Africa, Middle East, and Asia
- the project will cover the costs of travel, accommodation, and subsistence for students and professors.
- the school will provide experience and evidence to design outreach activities to schools and stakeholder organisations
- adding value: dissemination of the principles of equity, justice and fairness in energy transition to student population

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WP7 - Management and Coordination + WP8 Ethics requirements

Lucio Pisacane, Serena Tagliacozzo, Paola Trussardi, Marco Cellini, Nicolò Marchesini
CNR coordination team

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WP 7 STRUCTURE AND OBJECTIVES

- To provide optimal orientation through the rapid set-up of effective management and communication structures, guidance, and support;
- To guarantee transparency for consortium partners and the EC through appropriate project documentation, and to ensure compliance with the delivery deadlines of the deliverables.
- To maximize the effectiveness of the project activities, ensuring the achievement of project results through scientific and administrative coordination.
- To ensure efficiency, using resources wisely, avoiding duplication of efforts, and reducing waste of time and energy.
- To prepare and supervise the organization of consortium meetings
- To coordinate the contents and the timing of the different phases of the project.
- To guarantee the correct use and management of the data collected within gEneSys.
- To guarantee a relevant monitoring and evaluation to the project lifecycle

COLLABORATIVE VALUES

- Relationship and spirit of collaboration
- Additionality: collaborate makes the difference
- Support organizations with different backgrounds and act as a bridge
- Collaborative projects promote learning, trust and support early stage researchers
- Non judgmental attitudes

TASKS

- T7.1 Scientific Coordination
- T7.2 Overall Management
- T7.3 Administrative and financial coordination
- T7.4 Data management and alignment with the Open Science principles
- T7.5 Monitoring and Evaluation
- T8.1 Ethics requirements

T7.1 SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

- Management roles and responsibilities according to the CA;
- Foster communication and collaboration within the Steering Committee;
- Foster communication and collaboration between the Steering Committee, Work Package Leaders and the Advisory Board;
- Convene the advisory board, involving its members in the gEneSys strategies;
- Supervise the writing of project Technical Reports;
- Guidelines for carrying out the scientific activities and the standard procedures to coordinate partner contributions including quality check of deliverables

T7.2 OVERALL MANAGEMENT

- CNR will ensure the overall coordination of activities and tasks:
- Coordinate and taking responsibility for any communication with the European Commission Project Officer (e.g. possible amendments, delivery of reports and deliverables);
- Communicating with external organizations and stakeholders;
- Organizing the first Project Meeting (Kick off) in Rome (D7.1) (M2), the second Project Meeting in Germany (M9), the third Project Meeting in Poland (M19) and in London (M29), in collaboration with the resident partner.
- We plan to have emeetings on M24 + M33

Project Reporting

Duration: 36 months

Period: 01/02/2023 - 31/01/2026

Continuous Reporting ~ Periodic Reporting

Reporting

There's two types of reporting in the Grant Management Services:

- **Continuous Reporting:** available from the beginning of a project
- **Periodic Reporting:** available at the end of a reporting period
 - After M15 for RP1 → which covers M1-15 = 15 months 01/02/2023 - 30/04/2024
 - After M36 for RP2 → which covers M16-36 = 21 months 01/05/2024 - 31/01/2026

Periodic Reporting

The reporting process consists of several phase:

- **Step 1:** All beneficiaries receive a notification and log on to the Funding & Tenders Portal
- **Step 2:** All beneficiaries complete their own Financial Part (Financial Statement) and their contribution to the Technical Part of the Periodic Report. Beneficiaries e-sign and submit their Financial Parts to the Coordinator
 - A. Completing their own Financial Part and the financial report of their Affiliated Entity → this is the case of CNR, with VIU as AE
 - B. Completing their own contribution to the Technical Part of the Periodic Report
- **Step 3:** The Coordinator approves the elements of the Periodic Report & submits to the EU

Periodic Reporting

The reporting process consists of several phase:

- **Step 4:** The EU reviews the submitted Periodic Report and accepts, requests additional information or rejects it
- **Step 5a:** the Coordinator does not agree with the content of the Payment Letter and uploads observations
- **Step 5b:** The Coordinator agrees with the content of the Payment Letter and closes the process without observations
- **Step 6:** Interim/Final payment

alternatively

Budget

Beneficiaries		Estimated eligible costs							Estimated EU contribution				
		Direct costs					Indirect costs		Total costs	EU contribution to eligible costs			Maximum grant amount
		A. Personnel costs	B. Subcontracting costs	C. Purchase costs			D. Other cost categories	E. Indirect costs		Funding rate %	Maximum EU contribution	Requested EU contribution	
No.	Name	A.1 Employees (or equivalent);	B. Subcontracting	C.1 Travel and subsistence	C.2 Equipment	C.3 Other goods, works and	D.1 Internally invoiced	E. Indirect costs					
1	CNR-IRPPS	448.000,00 €	0,00 €	30.000,00 €	2.000,00 €	20.000,00 €	0,00 €	125.000,00 €	625.000,00 €	100	625.000,00 €	625.000,00 €	625.000,00 €
1.1	(AE) VIU	3.000,00 €	0,00 €	24.966,00 €	0,00 €	1.185,00 €	0,00 €	7.287,75 €	36.438,75 €	100	36.438,75 €	36.438,75 €	36.438,75 €
2	UJ	216.200,00 €	0,00 €	10.000,00 €	5.000,00 €	15.000,00 €	0,00 €	61.550,00 €	307.750,00 €	100	307.750,00 €	307.750,00 €	307.750,00 €
3	ENEA	320.000,00 €	0,00 €	10.000,00 €	5.000,00 €	5.000,00 €	0,00 €	85.000,00 €	425.000,00 €	100	425.000,00 €	425.000,00 €	425.000,00 €
4	Fraunhofer	355.200,00 €	295.000,00 €	10.000,00 €	5.000,00 €	3.000,00 €	0,00 €	93.300,00 €	761.500,00 €	100	761.500,00 €	761.500,00 €	761.500,00 €
5	AIMS Rwanda	42.000,00 €	0,00 €	6.000,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	12.000,00 €	60.000,00 €	100	60.000,00 €	60.000,00 €	60.000,00 €
6	Portia gGmbH	282.000,00 €	0,00 €	40.560,00 €	0,00 €	30.080,00 €	0,00 €	88.160,00 €	440.800,00 €	100	440.800,00 €	440.800,00 €	440.800,00 €
7	(AP) Imperial	266.920,00 €	0,00 €	11.398,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	69.579,50 €	347.897,50 €	0	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €
TOT		1.933.320,00 €	295.000,00 €	142.924,00 €	17.000,00 €	74.265,00 €	0,00 €	541.877,25 €	3.004.386,25 €		2.656.488,75 €	2.656.488,75 €	2.656.488,75 €

Costs reporting

Budget categories available for the calculation and the reporting of project costs:

A. **Personnel costs**

B. **Subcontracting** = implementation of an action task as described in the G.A. Fraunhofer

C. **Other direct costs**

- travel costs
- equipment costs
- other goods, works and services

E. **Indirect costs** (*overheads* = 25% flat rate of direct costs)

A. Personnel Costs

- Staff already employed in the HI
- Staff hired on the project/action
- other specific cases

Calculation of the personnel costs (Horizon Europe vs. H2020):

Personnel costs = daily rate x days worked in the project

Daily rate = $\frac{\text{actual annual personnel costs for the person}}{215 \text{ (working days per year)}}$

B. Subcontracting

- Subcontracting must be specified in the Grant Agreement.
- Subcontracting means that action tasks are outsourced to external third parties.
A subcontractor is called upon by a beneficiary to implement an action task and issues an invoice for the service provided at regular market prices.
- Subcontracting does not generate indirect costs for the beneficiary.

C. ODC

1. Travel costs

2. Equipment costs (purchase and rental/leasing)

$$\text{Depreciation} = A/B \times C \times D$$

A = the period in months during which the durable equipment is used for the project after invoicing

B = the depreciation period for the durable equipment, as per regular accounting practice for the HI

C = the actual cost of the durable equipment

D = the percentage of usage of the durable equipment for the project

3. Other goods, works and services

included CFS costs (if the EC contribution is > 430,000 EUR) → CNR - Fraunhofer - Portia

T7.4 DATA MANAGEMENT AND ALIGNMENT WITH THE OPEN SCIENCE PRINCIPLES

Under the supervision of the CNR, an appropriate **Data Management Plan (DMP)** will be drafted at the beginning of the project (D7.2) and will be continuously revised (D7.9). The DMP will be produced as an outcome of **consultation among all partners**, setting ethics indicators for all WPs, and it will detail the plan for **data collection, storage, and analysis**, ensuring that the project is proceeding in a responsible and ethically acceptable manner according to recommended **Open Science principles**. Data will be made publicly available except for cases in which the data are presented in an aggregated or anonymized form due to confidentiality issues or compliance with any other regulations. The DMP will also describe data repositories to be used by the consortium for storage and sharing of administrative data.

T7.4 DATA MANAGEMENT AND ALIGNMENT WITH THE OPEN SCIENCE PRINCIPLES

Main activities:

- The **first draft** of the DMP (+ Protection of Personal Data - POPD) is due to M6 (31 July 2023) → D7.2 - public.
- Constantly updated up to its **final version** due to M18 (31 July 2024) → D7.9 - public.

Based on

- **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable);
- Open Science approach (e.g., Open Data, Codes, Publications);
- **2016/679 GDPR** concerning the Data Protection Policies.

T7.4 DATA MANAGEMENT AND ALIGNMENT WITH THE OPEN SCIENCE PRINCIPLES

- **WP1 – Gendered analysis of knowledge creation landscape for energy transition**
 - T1.5. Gendered assessment of stakeholder organisations in sustainable energy systems: pilot qualitative interviews + survey (CNR)
- **WP2 – Exploring gendered intersectional patterns in citizen's behaviours and orientations towards energy transition**
 - T2.1 Exploring intersectional power-gender relations: survey (Fraunhofer CeRRI)
 - T2.2 Co-creation with a group of experts of an intersectional theoretical framework: Delphi survey (Fraunhofer CeRRI)
 - T2.3 Case study analyses: interviews (Fraunhofer CeRRI)
- **WP4 - Transforming International cooperation between Europe and Africa on advancing gender participation**
 - T4.2 Identify the needs and opportunities to advance women in Africa as energy transition researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders (AIMS)
 - T4.5 Analyse how the concepts of equity, inclusion, justice, and fairness in the context of SDG7 targets are interpreted by students in Africa (AIMS)

T7.4 DATA MANAGEMENT AND ALIGNMENT WITH THE OPEN SCIENCE PRINCIPLES

- **Data:** Joint controllers (art.26 GDPR)?
- **Documents platform:** OSF, Zenodo?
- **Collaborative platform:** TEAMS
- **Repositories**
 - Open data: [CESSDA](#) Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
 - Open code: [CESSDA](#) Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
 - Open preprint: [Open Research Europe – ORE](#)
 - Open access publications: open green/gold.

T7.5 – MONITORING AND EVALUATION

TWO M&E STREAMS

1. The project activities, outputs, outcomes (qualitative and quantitative indicators)

Possible questions: Did the project achieve its general and specific objectives? Was the project on time? Did the project reach the intended impact? How well did the individual partners work together to realise the project's activities?

Possible instruments: i) A review and analysis of the deliverables produced by the project. ii) Observations of interactions at the meetings. iii) Surveys of personnel from partnering institutions

2. The engagement of relevant stakeholders (qualitative and quantitative indicators) in collaboration with PORTIA

Possible questions : did the project reach out to relevant stakeholders? Did it incorporate stakeholders' needs, views and inputs in the project activities and outcomes? Did the project worked in synergy with sister projects to maximise impact?

Possible instruments: i) observations of organized stakeholder engagement events; ii) surveys administered to stakeholders engaged; iii) Advisory Board's formal and informal feedback

Approach: Formative evaluation (evaluation conducted during the course of the project to improve project's activities, outcomes and outputs);

T8.1 - ETHICS REQUIREMENTS

Objectives:

- To set-up and implement the mechanisms needed to ensure the respect of the highest ethical standards in research activities
- To ensure that the (RRI) approach is adopted.
- To supervise and guarantee the application of ethical and security measures.

Activities:

- Each implementing partner organization will name a responsible for ethical issues (M2).
- Under the coordination of the CNR, gEneSys will form an internal ethics committee (M2), composed of each institution's responsible. The ethics committee will draft an ethical management plan (D8.1.) (M6).
- In particular, the Ethical Management Plan will deal with the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants, and the informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans.

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gEneSys – Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities for Just Energy Systems

Kick-off meeting 07-08 March

Policy context

Jeanne LENDERS
Policy Officer – Gender Sector
Democracy and European Values Unit
DG Research & Innovation
Jeanne.lenders@ec.europa.eu

Policy Context

#EUstrivesformore #vdLcommission

A New Push for European Democracy

- Gender equality and inclusion high on the agenda of the vdL Commission
- Commissioner for Equality (Helena Dalli)
- Mariya Gabriel, Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth
- Nicolas Schmit, Commissioner for Jobs and Social Rights
- Kadri Simson, Commissioner for Energy

Political guidelines – a “Union of Equality”

- 6 Equality Strategies adopted:
 - [Gender Equality Strategy 2020 – 2025 \(05/03/2020\)](#)
 - [EU Anti-racism Action Plan 2020-2025 \(18/09/2020\)](#)
 - [EU Roma strategic framework for equality, inclusion and participation \(07/10/2020\)](#)
 - [LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020-2025 \(12/11/2020\)](#)
 - [Gender Action Plan III – a priority of EU external action \(25/11/2020\)](#)
 - [Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021 – 2030 \(03/03/2021\)](#)
 - In March 2022 the Commission adopted a proposal for a [Directive on combating violence against women and domestic violence](#)
 - In December 2022 the Commission adopted [two proposals for strengthening equality bodies](#)
- **[State of play](#)** in tracking equality commitments

EC Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025

Communication on 'A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025'

Released on 5 March 2020

R&I and Horizon Europe are explicitly addressed:

- New measures to strengthen gender equality in Horizon Europe:
 - **Gender equality plan** as an eligibility criterion for applicants (from 2022 onwards)
 - **Funding for gender and intersectional research** will also be made available:
 - Feminisms for a new age of democracy (HORIZON-CL2-**2021**-DEMOCRACY-01-03)
 - **Gender and social, economic and cultural empowerment** (HORIZON-CL2-**2022**-TRANSFORMATIONS-01-05)
 - Boosting women-led innovation in farming and rural areas (HORIZON-CL6-**2022**-COMMUNITIES-01-0)

Delivering the European Green Deal

- Reducing net emissions by at least **55% by 2030** compared to 1990 and becoming the first **climate neutral continent by 2050** → [European Climate Law](#) (30/06/2021)

Whole economy approach:

- **A socially fair transition:** tackling inequality and energy poverty through climate action
- **A competitive transition:** New opportunities through industrial and sectoral change
- **A green transition:** Protecting nature and increasing Europe's natural carbon sink

Socially Fair Transition

- [Social Climate Fund](#): financially support vulnerable people and businesses most impacted by the reform of the emissions trading system (new carbon pricing for fossil fuels)
- [Council Recommendation on ensuring a fair transition towards climate neutrality](#) (14/12/2021)
 - Equal access essential services, including energy, transport, sanitation, financial services and digital communications, incl. for women
 - Inclusive and high-quality education in skills for the green transitions (STEM) for women and other underrepresented groups
 - Inclusive participation in policy design and implementation to empower civil society, including women, youth, and people with disabilities

R&I initiatives on gender equality in the green transition

- **Women TechEU**: support scheme for women-led deep-tech start-ups (incl. clean tech and bio tech); 70000 EUR with tailored mentoring and coaching to bring their business to the next level
- **Study on gender balance in the R&I field to improve the role of women in the energy transition** – funded under Horizon Europe Cluster 5 ‘Climate, Energy and Mobility’ 2021 – 2022 Work Programme
 - Budget: EUR 900.000, Duration 12 months (kick-off meeting in Jan 2023)
 - Understanding of the impact of gender imbalances in the energy sector, specifically at the level of employment in technologies and innovation.
- **Horizon Magazine**: [Women’s full participation in renewables is essential for a fair and green future | Research and Innovation \(europa.eu\)](#)
- Report on “[Energy poverty and gender in the EU: the missing debate](#)” - JRC policy brief

Horizon Europe

Gender equality: strengthened crosscutting priority in Horizon Europe

- Article 7(6) & Recital 53 of [Framework Regulation](#) ; Articles 2(2)(e) & 6(3)(e) of the [Specific Programme](#)

Three levels:

Gender Equality Plan: Eligibility Criterion for public bodies, research organisations and higher education institutions established in a Member State or Associated Country

Integration of the Gender Dimension in R&I content: mandatory by default, unless specified otherwise in topic description. **Award Criterion** under *Excellence* (methodology)

→ **Methods and case studies in [Gendered Innovations 2 Expert Report](#)**

→ **Additional guidance in [Horizon Europe Programme Guide](#)** ('gender equality & inclusiveness')

Gender Balance in research teams: Ranking Criterion for *ex aequo* proposals

+ Researchers can declare their gender along three categories: **woman, man, non-binary**

HORIZON EUROPE

Innovative research on Social and Economic Transformations (2022)

Destination: Social and economic transformations

Aim:

Enhance employment, education, social fairness and tackle inequalities

Expected impact:

Social and economic resilience and sustainability are strengthened through a better understanding of the **social, ethical, political and economic impacts** of drivers of change (such as technology, globalisation, demographics, mobility and migration) and their interplay.

Why did we publish this topic?

→ Re-examine power relations in light of economic crises, pandemics, and the **climate emergency**

Objectives:

- Better understanding of gendered power relations across the **social and economic spheres**, taking into account intersectionality
- Support Sustainable Development Goal 5

- Propose a **theoretical framework** to understand the formation of gendered power hierarchies leading to systematic forms of discriminations
- Develop **solutions** to address inequalities and underlying causes related to society's perception and construction of gender norms and identities

Sister projects

- [ReIncluGen](#) (January 2023): Rethinking Inclusion and Gender empowerment – University of Antwerpen (Belgium)
- [gEneSys](#) (March 2023): Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities for Just Energy Systems. Coordinator: Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche - CNR (Italy)
- [RE-WIRING](#): Realising Girls' and Women's Inclusion, Representation and Empowerment. Coordinator: Universiteit Utrecht (Netherlands)

Also: **3 projects** funded under the **Cluster 5** call '[Fostering a just transition in Europe](#)' (10mill EUR: Tandem, AdJUST, BOLSTER)

What we expect

Write short policy briefs

Don't forget to invite us to events

Organise a cluster event with the other projects

Keep us in the loop!

What we can do for you

- We disseminate Horizon Europe funded research across the Commission and other EU institutions and consider key findings in our policymaking
- We promote your research through our media channels (e.g. Twitter, Horizon Magazine)
- Ongoing Horizon projects help us define future research funding needs

HORIZON EUROPE

Useful Resources

Gender Equality in R&I policy updates

Gender equality in research and innovation

Achieving gender equality in research, how it relates to the European Research Area, networks and news.

PAGE CONTENTS

[The Commission's gender equality strategy](#)

[Gender equality in Horizon Europe](#)

[Gender Equality Plans as an eligibility criterion in Horizon Europe](#)

[Gender equality in the European Research Area \(ERA\)](#)

[Gender mainstreaming through the integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content](#)

[She Figures report - monitoring gender equality in research and innovation](#)

[Fostering women's participation in STEM](#)

[Gender equality and coronavirus](#)

[Networks](#)

The Commission's gender equality strategy

The European Commission is committed to promoting gender equality in research and innovation.

It is part of the European Commission [Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025](#), which sets out the Commission's broader commitment to equality across all EU policies.

In addition, the EU has a well-established regulatory framework on gender equality, including binding directives, which apply widely across the labour market including the research sector.

DRIVE THE CHANGE

This prize will reward academic and/or research organisations with a Gender Equality Plan in the following 3 categories:

- Sustainable gender equality champions
- Newcomer gender equality champions
- Inclusive gender equality champions

APPLY NOW!

@EUScienceInnov
#UnionOfEquality #GenderEquality #GEP

EU Award for Gender Equality Champions

European Commission

https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en

[Approaches to inclusive gender equality in R&I](#)

New
EU Award for Gender Equality Champions
for academic & research organisations driving the change towards gender equality in R&I

3 categories to apply

- Most sustainable GEP
- Best newcomer GEP
- Most inclusive GEP

Winner announcement: 08 March 2023

Thank you!

For questions and further information, please contact:
RTD-GENDERINRESEARCH@ec.europa.eu

#HorizonEU

<http://ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe>

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